

D6.1: Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

WP : WP6: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

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Disclaimer of Warranties

This document has been prepared by ESTELAR project partners as an account of work carried out within the framework of the GA contract N° 101192574.

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This deliverable has used a standard methodology already defined by partner R2M and developed in previous EU funded project. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the conditions of the Grant Agreement for ESTELAR project (Grant Agreement number: 101192574).

Executive Summary

This document presents the **Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan** for **ESTELAR**. As the foundational strategy document produced under Work Package 6 (WP6), led by R2M ES, this plan outlines the initial framework, objectives, target audiences, key messages, channels, tools, and activities for communicating the project's aims and progress, disseminating its results, and managing its exploitation potential throughout its 36-month duration. ESTELAR aims to significantly advance the modernization of European power grids by developing and validating cutting-edge technologies for the **virtualization of electrical substations**. This initiative addresses critical needs for enhanced grid resilience, efficiency, security, and the effective integration of renewable energy sources, thereby contributing to the EU's clean energy transition goals.

The CDE strategy detailed herein is **integrated and targeted**, aiming to:

- **Raise awareness** of ESTELAR's objectives, innovative three-pillar approach (advanced communications, robust computation, Digital Substation of the Future - DSoF), and progress among diverse stakeholders.
- **Effectively disseminate** technical results, findings from Virtualization Testing Lab (VTL) validations, and generated knowledge to relevant scientific, industrial, policy, and standardization communities.
- **Actively engage** key stakeholders, including system operators (DSOs/TSOs), technology providers, researchers, and regulators, for collaboration, feedback, and community building.
- **Establish the foundation for exploitation** by identifying preliminary Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and outlining the strategy for managing Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).

This plan details the specific **channels and activities** to be employed, including the project website, social media presence, scientific and technical publications, participation in key industry events and conferences, stakeholder workshops, and development of promotional materials. It also establishes the **management structure** for CDE within the consortium, defining the roles and responsibilities of the WP leader and all partners. Furthermore, it introduces the **monitoring framework**, including initial Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and a preliminary **risk assessment** with mitigation strategies.

As the **first version**, this CDE plan provides the essential roadmap for the initial project phases. It is a **living document** that will be continuously monitored, evaluated, and updated in subsequent deliverables (D6.6, D6.8, etc.) to reflect project advancements, incorporate emerging results, and adapt to the evolving

stakeholder landscape, ensuring maximum impact for the ESTELAR project. The active participation and contribution of all consortium partners are crucial for its successful implementation.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Deliverable

This deliverable, D6.1, presents the first version of the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) Plan for the Horizon Europe project ESTELAR (Effective Substation TEchnologies for Advanced viRtualization), Grant Agreement No. 101192574. Its primary purpose is to establish the foundational strategy and framework that will guide all CDE activities throughout the project's 36-month duration.

This initial plan outlines the strategic objectives for communicating the project's aims and progress, disseminating its results effectively, and laying the groundwork for the future exploitation of its innovations. It identifies key target audiences, defines core project messages, selects appropriate communication and dissemination channels and tools, and introduces the methodology for identifying and managing the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and associated Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).

As the designated "First Version" (due M6), this document serves as a baseline. It is intended to be a living document, subject to iterative refinement and updates in subsequent CDE deliverables (specifically D6.6 - Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan M24, and potentially consolidated final reporting) as the project progresses, tangible results emerge, the stakeholder landscape evolves, and feedback is gathered

1.2 ESTELAR Project Overview

ESTELAR is dedicated to modernizing power grids to accommodate the increasing influx of renewable energy sources and enhance overall energy efficiency. The project focuses specifically on the **virtualization of substations** as a critical enabler for improving the grid's sustainability and resilience. By redefining the operation and concept of these key components within the power grid infrastructure, ESTELAR aims to accelerate the energy transition towards carbon neutrality.

The project's approach is built upon three innovative pillars:

1. **Advanced Communication Strategies:** Enhancing substation communication systems for seamless, secure, and real-time integration of physical and virtual components, considering both LAN and WAN scopes.
2. **Robust Computational Framework:** Boosting the processing and data handling capabilities of substations across edge and cloud platforms to meet future computational demands and enable advanced analytics.

3. **Digital Substation of the Future (DSoF) Architecture:** Developing a modular, scalable, and cybersecure substation architecture that integrates advanced monitoring, protection, and control functions, leveraging digital twinning and virtualized Protection, Automation and Control (vPAC).

To ensure the efficacy and readiness of these technologies, ESTELAR will conduct rigorous validations in two dedicated **Virtualization Testing Laboratories (VTLs)** located in Spain (coordinated by CIRCE) and The Netherlands (coordinated by TUD). These facilities provide realistic, controlled environments to test, refine, and validate the developed technologies (TRL4 objective) before potential wider implementation.

Ultimately, ESTELAR seeks to facilitate renewable energy integration, bolster grid resilience against disturbances and cyber threats, support wider electrification efforts, and contribute significantly to the EU's strategic goals for a climate-neutral energy system.

1.3 Link to Grant Agreement Obligations

This CDE Plan is developed in direct response to the obligations outlined in the ESTELAR Grant Agreement (GA No. 101192574). The execution of this plan is essential for fulfilling the project's contractual requirements, particularly:

Article 17 – Communication, Dissemination and Visibility: This article mandates comprehensive actions to promote the project and its results to multiple audiences (including media and the public), ensure the visibility of EU funding (correctly displaying the EU emblem and funding statement), guarantee the quality and accuracy of information disseminated, and implement specific CDE activities outlined in the GA's Annex 1. It also requires adherence to Open Science principles regarding publications and research data.

Article 16 – Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) – Background and Results – Access Rights and Rights of Use: This article governs the management of knowledge generated within the project. The CDE plan is intrinsically linked, as IPR strategies (protection, licensing, etc.) directly influence *what* results can be disseminated, *how*, and *when*, and define the pathways for exploitation. Managing background and foreground IP effectively is crucial for both dissemination and exploitation.

Annex 1 – Description of the Action (DoA): The DoA details the project's objectives, work plan, and expected impacts. The CDE plan aims to communicate and disseminate these elements effectively. WP6, as described in the DoA (GA p. 75, 85-86), specifically covers the tasks related to this plan.

Annex 5 – Specific Rules: This annex (GA p. 157-172) contains specific rules regarding IPR, Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation which are considered and integrated into this CDE strategy.

Compliance with these articles and annexes is a core requirement, and this plan provides the framework for achieving it.

1.4 Structure of the Document

This document is structured to provide a clear and comprehensive overview of the initial CDE strategy for ESTELAR.

Section 2 details the overall C&D strategy, outlining the objectives and methodology.

Section 3 identifies the key target audiences and stakeholders for ESTELAR's CDE activities.

Section 4 outlines the core messages the project aims to convey.

Section 5 describes the specific communication and dissemination channels, tools, and planned activities.

Section 6 introduces the initial Exploitation strategy, including the approach to KER identification and IPR management.

Section 7 covers the management structure and responsibilities for implementing the CDE plan.

Section 8 defines the monitoring approach and sets initial Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

Section 9 presents a risk assessment related to CDE activities and proposes mitigation measures.

Section 10 provides concluding remarks.

Annexes include templates for tracking CDE activities and reporting on events.

2 Communication & Dissemination (C&D) Strategy and Objectives

This section outlines the overarching strategy and specific objectives that will guide the Communication and Dissemination (C&D) activities for the ESTELAR project. The strategy aims to maximize the project's impact by effectively reaching relevant audiences, sharing knowledge and results, and paving the way for future exploitation.

2.1 Overall, Vision and Ambition

The **vision** for ESTELAR's Communication and Dissemination strategy is to position the project as a leading European initiative advancing the critical field of **substation virtualization** as a cornerstone technology for a **resilient, efficient, and decarbonized energy grid**. Our ambition is to ensure that ESTELAR's innovative approaches, technological advancements, and validated results are widely recognized, understood, and utilized by key stakeholders across the energy sector and beyond.

We aim to move beyond simple reporting of activities. The CDE strategy will proactively shape the narrative around ESTELAR, highlighting its contribution to:

Grid Modernization: Showcasing how virtualization enhances flexibility, control, and automation.

Renewable Energy Integration: Demonstrating how ESTELAR facilitates the reliable integration of variable RES.

Grid Resilience & Security: Communicating the project's efforts in enhancing grid stability and cybersecurity in virtualized environments.

Energy Transition: Positioning ESTELAR as a key enabler for achieving EU climate and energy targets.

Through targeted and consistent CDE efforts, we intend to build a strong identity for ESTELAR, foster a collaborative ecosystem around its themes, and ultimately contribute to the accelerated adoption of advanced digital substation technologies across Europe.

2.2 C&D Objectives

Based on the overall vision, the following specific objectives have been defined for ESTELAR's CDE activities:

1. **Raise Awareness and Understanding:** To inform key target audiences and the wider public about the ESTELAR project's rationale, objectives, approach (including the three pillars and VTLs), consortium, and progress. This

involves creating a clear understanding of the challenges ESTELAR addresses and the innovative solutions it proposes.

2. **Effective Dissemination of Results:** To share the project's research findings, technical developments (e.g., DSoF architecture, communication protocols, computational frameworks, vPAC, cybersecurity measures), validated results from VTLs, and generated knowledge with relevant scientific, technical, industrial, and policy-making communities to foster uptake, further research, and standardization efforts.
3. **Stakeholder Engagement and Community Building:** To actively engage with identified stakeholder groups (including system operators, technology providers, researchers, regulators) throughout the project lifecycle to gather input, solicit feedback, foster collaboration, build trust, and create a community of interest around substation virtualization and related technologies.
4. **Support Exploitation Pathways:** To prepare the ground for the future exploitation of ESTELAR's results by clearly articulating their value proposition, identifying potential applications and markets, managing Intellectual Property Rights effectively, and connecting potential results owners with relevant end-users or industry players.
5. **Ensure Visibility and Compliance:** To guarantee the visibility of the project and the contribution of EU funding (Horizon Europe) in all CDE activities, and to ensure full compliance with the Grant Agreement obligations regarding communication, dissemination, Open Access to publications, and FAIR principles for research data management.

2.3 Methodology and Approach

The ESTELAR CDE strategy will adopt an integrated, targeted, and adaptive methodology:

Integrated Approach: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation activities will be planned and executed in a coordinated manner, primarily under the leadership of WP6 (R2M ES), ensuring consistency and maximizing synergies. While distinct in their primary focus, these activities often overlap and reinforce each other.

Targeted Communication: Recognizing that different audiences have different interests and levels of technical understanding, CDE activities will be tailored. Messages, channels, and formats will be selected based on the specific objective and the target audience being addressed, moving from general awareness to deep technical dissemination or specific exploitation discussions as appropriate.

Staged Implementation: While activities will run in parallel, the CDE efforts will generally follow a progression, aligning with the project's lifecycle:

Phase 1 (Awareness, approx. M1-M18): Focus on establishing the project identity, communicating the vision and objectives, building the initial stakeholder community, and setting up core communication channels (website, social media).

Phase 2 (Understanding & Engagement, approx. M12-M30): Emphasis on disseminating initial findings, technical progress, engaging stakeholders for feedback through workshops/events, and refining the understanding of exploitable results.

Phase 3 (Action & Uptake, approx. M24-M36+): Focus on disseminating validated results from VTLs, promoting KERs, consolidating exploitation plans, demonstrating impact, and ensuring long-term accessibility of key outputs.

Multi-channel Strategy: A diverse mix of channels and tools will be employed (detailed in Section 5), including digital platforms (website, social media), publications (scientific, technical), events (conferences, workshops), direct engagement, and promotional materials, to maximize reach and impact.

Iterative and Adaptive: This plan (D6.1) provides the initial framework. The strategy, activities, and KPIs will be regularly monitored and evaluated (Section 8). Based on project progress, emerging results, stakeholder feedback, and performance analysis, the plan will be adapted and updated in subsequent deliverables (D6.6, D6.8) to ensure continued relevance and effectiveness.

Collaborative Execution: The success of the CDE strategy relies on the active involvement of all consortium partners in contributing content, participating in activities, leveraging their networks, and providing feedback.

This strategic framework ensures that CDE activities are not merely an add-on but an integral part of the ESTELAR project, driving its visibility, impact, and the eventual uptake of its results. The specific implementation details are elaborated in the following sections.

3 Target Audiences and Stakeholders

Effective communication and dissemination require a clear understanding of the intended audiences, which also will input Exploitation activities (see Section 6). This section identifies the key groups and stakeholders relevant to the ESTELAR project, outlines their potential interests, and explains their importance to the project's success and impact.

3.1 Identification Methodology

The identification of target audiences and stakeholders for ESTELAR is an ongoing process that began during the proposal stage and will be refined throughout the project lifecycle. The initial identification is based on:

Project Scope and Objectives: Analyzing the core technical areas (advanced communications, computation, DSoF, cybersecurity) and overall goals (grid modernization, resilience, RES integration) defined in the Description of Action (DoA).

Consortium Composition and Expertise: Leveraging the knowledge and existing networks of the ESTELAR partners (CIRCE, TUD, SIEMENS, CUERVA, 3SI, SOC-E, R2M ES/IT, and Associated Partner STEDIN), who represent key parts of the value chain (research, technology development, system operation).

Value Chain Analysis: Considering the actors involved in the development, deployment, operation, regulation, and standardization of substation technologies and smart grid solutions.

Impact Pathways: Identifying groups whose actions or decisions are crucial for the uptake and exploitation of ESTELAR's results or who will be significantly affected by them.

This initial list will be further developed and detailed within WP6, potentially involving stakeholder mapping exercises and feedback loops to prioritize engagement efforts and tailor communication strategies effectively.

3.2 Key Stakeholder Groups

Based on the methodology above, the following key stakeholder groups have been identified for ESTELAR's CDE activities:

1. **Energy System Operators:** Including Distribution System Operators (DSOs, like project partner CUERVA and AP STEDIN) and Transmission System Operators (TSOs).
2. **Technology Providers & Industry:** Companies developing and supplying hardware (e.g., IEDs, communication equipment, servers), software (e.g., SCADA, automation platforms, simulation tools, cybersecurity solutions), and integration services for substations and power grids. Project partners

SIEMENS and SOC-E fall into this category, alongside other major vendors and specialized SMEs like partner 3SI.

3. **Research Community & Academia:** Universities (like project partner TUD), Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs, like project coordinator CIRCE), researchers, and students working in relevant fields (power systems, communications, computer science, cybersecurity, energy policy). This also includes related EU and national R&I projects.
4. **Policymakers & Regulators:** European institutions (European Commission directorates like DG ENER, DG CNECT; Agencies like CINEA, ENISA, ACER) and national energy ministries, regulatory authorities, and government agencies responsible for energy policy, grid development, cybersecurity regulations, and research funding.
5. **Standardisation Bodies:** International (e.g., IEC, particularly TC 57; IEEE), European (e.g., CEN, CENELEC, ETSI), and national bodies involved in developing standards relevant to substation automation, communication protocols (IEC 61850), interoperability, and cybersecurity.
6. **Industry Associations & Platforms:** European and national associations representing utilities, technology providers, or specific interests (e.g., Smart Grids platforms like ETIP SNET, E.DSO; cybersecurity alliances; communication technology forums). In particular, two suggested targets are vPAC Alliance (<https://vpacalliance.com/>) and CIGRE's working group OR-WG B5.84, "Recommendations and constraints for development and interfacing of virtual IEDs implemented in PACS"
7. **(Potentially) Wider Industry End-Users:** Large industrial consumers or infrastructure operators whose operations rely heavily on stable and efficient power grids.
8. **(Potentially) General Public:** While not a primary target for detailed technical dissemination, the public is relevant for communicating the societal benefits (reliability, RES integration support, energy transition) and ensuring social acceptance of new grid technologies.

3.3 Stakeholder Analysis (Initial Assessment)

A preliminary analysis of the relevance and potential interests of each key group is provided below (Table 1). This analysis will inform the tailoring of messages and the selection of appropriate CDE channels and activities. It highlights the diverse interests and importance of various groups to ESTELAR. The CDE strategy will prioritize engagement with those groups most critical for feedback, validation, dissemination, and future uptake, particularly System Operators, Technology Providers, the Research Community, and relevant Standardisation

Bodies, while ensuring broader communication reaches policymakers and other relevant parties.

Table 1. Stakeholder Analysis

Stakeholder Group	Relevance & Importance to ESTELAR	Potential Interests in ESTELAR
Energy System Operators (DSO/TSO)	Direct potential end-users/adopters of ESTELAR solutions. Provide essential operational context, requirements, and validation data (partners CUERVA, STEDIN). Critical for market uptake.	Improved grid reliability, resilience, security; cost-effective modernization pathways; enhanced operational efficiency; solutions for managing RES/DERs; interoperability; compliance with future standards/regulations.
Technology Providers & Industry	Key partners in development (SIEMENS, SOC-E, 3SI). Potential exploiters of results (licensing, new products/services). Competitors and collaborators.	New market opportunities; technical specifications & requirements; validation of technologies in VTLs; insights into future grid architectures; standardization trends; partnership opportunities.
Research Community & Academia	Peer group for scientific validation and dissemination. Source of collaboration and future expertise. Partners TUD and CIRCE are central.	Novel scientific findings; advanced methodologies (simulation, communication, computation, cybersecurity); access to VTLs/data (under FAIR principles); publications; networking & clustering opportunities; training potential.
Policymakers & Regulators	Shape the regulatory and market framework influencing technology adoption. Set targets (energy transition, cybersecurity). Funders (EC/CINEA).	Evidence for policy development (grid modernization, cybersecurity, digitalization); alignment with EU energy/climate goals; security of supply implications; innovation potential; socio-economic impacts; standardization support.
Standardisation Bodies	Define the technical standards (esp. IEC 61850 and related communication/security standards) crucial for interoperability and market acceptance.	Insights into performance/interoperability of new technologies implementing/extending standards; use cases; feedback for standard evolution; potential expert contributions from partners.
Industry Associations & Platforms	Act as multipliers for dissemination. Represent collective industry interests. Provide platforms for networking and showcasing results.	Technological trends; innovative solutions; best practices; policy developments; networking opportunities; potential for joint workshops or position papers.

Wider Industry End-Users	Benefit indirectly from enhanced grid reliability and efficiency. May influence DSO/TSO investment priorities.	Understanding impacts on power quality, supply security, and potential future energy service offerings.
General Public	Taxpayers funding the research. Ultimate beneficiaries of a stable, affordable, sustainable energy system. Relevant for social acceptance.	Understanding the project's contribution to energy security, affordability, sustainability, and the green transition; transparency about EU funding usage.

4 Key Messages

Key messages are the core, concise points of information that ESTELAR aims to communicate consistently across all CDE activities. They distil the project's essence, highlighting its innovation, relevance, and value proposition for different audiences. Effective key messages are crucial for ensuring clarity, building understanding, and achieving the project's communication and dissemination objectives outlined in Section 2.

These messages will be tailored in their specific delivery (e.g., level of technical detail, emphasis) depending on the channel and target audience, but the fundamental concepts will remain consistent

4.1 Overall Project Messages

These top-level messages encapsulate the main purpose and contribution of the ESTELAR project:

ESTELAR pioneers advanced substation virtualization: We develop and validate groundbreaking technologies to digitally transform electrical substations, paving the way for a more modern, adaptable, and intelligent power grid.

ESTELAR enhances grid resilience, efficiency, and security: Our integrated solutions, focusing on advanced communications, robust computation, and a secure Digital Substation of the Future (DSofF) architecture, address key challenges in today's energy system, making the grid more reliable and secure against disruptions and cyber threats.

ESTELAR accelerates the clean energy transition: By enabling better management of grid complexity and facilitating the seamless integration of renewable energy sources, ESTELAR provides critical digital infrastructure supporting Europe's climate neutrality goals and energy independence objectives.

ESTELAR provides validated, practical solutions: Through rigorous testing in dedicated Virtualization Testing Laboratories (VTLs), ESTELAR moves beyond concepts to deliver validated, interoperable technologies ready for consideration in real-world grid modernization strategies.

4.2 Messages Tailored per Target Audience

Building on the overall messages, the following points emphasize the specific value ESTELAR offers to key stakeholder groups:

For Energy System Operators (DSOs/TSOs):

- ESTELAR offers **validated and cost-effective pathways** to modernize your substations through virtualization, improving operational efficiency and extending asset life.
- Our solutions enhance **grid resilience and cybersecurity**, helping you manage increasing complexity and threats in a digitalized environment.
- We provide tools and architectures to better **integrate and manage renewable energy sources** and distributed energy resources (DERs) connected to your network.
- Benefit from **interoperable solutions** tested in realistic environments, reducing vendor lock-in and deployment risks.

For Technology Providers & Industry:

- ESTELAR defines **future requirements and architectures** for digital substations, revealing **new market opportunities** for your products and services (hardware, software, cybersecurity, integration).
- Leverage ESTELAR's **Virtualization Testing Labs** as unique platforms to test, validate, and showcase the interoperability and performance of your innovative solutions.
- Collaborate with leading researchers and utilities to **co-develop and refine technologies** aligned with emerging industry needs and standards.
- Gain insights into **standardization trends** and position your company at the forefront of substation virtualization technology.

For Research Community & Academia:

- ESTELAR tackles **cutting-edge research challenges** at the intersection of power systems, advanced communications (e.g., TSN, 5G/6G applicability), edge/cloud computing, cybersecurity, and control systems.
- Engage with the project for **collaboration opportunities, access to unique VTL infrastructure**, and potential use of project data (aligned with FAIR principles).
- Contribute to and benefit from **high-impact scientific publications** and the advancement of knowledge in critical energy infrastructure digitalization.

For Policymakers & Regulators:

- ESTELAR demonstrates tangible **technological solutions supporting EU energy policy goals**, including the Green Deal, Fit for 55 targets, grid modernization, and cybersecurity resilience.
- We provide **evidence-based insights** into the capabilities, benefits, and requirements (including regulatory aspects) of substation virtualization for informing future policies and grid development plans.

- The project showcases **European innovation leadership** in essential digital technologies for the critical energy infrastructure sector.

For Standardisation Bodies:

- ESTELAR offers **practical implementation experience and performance data** relevant to standards like IEC 61850, IEC 62351 (cybersecurity), TSN, and others in virtualized substation contexts.
- Our work helps identify potential **gaps, ambiguities, or needs for evolution** in current standards to fully accommodate virtualization and advanced communication/computation paradigms.
- We provide **realistic use cases and test results** that can inform the development of future standards and interoperability profiles.

5 Communication & Dissemination Channels, Tools, and Activities

This section details the specific channels, tools, and activities that will be employed to achieve the Communication and Dissemination (C&D) objectives outlined in Section 2. The selection is based on reaching the identified target audiences (Section 3) effectively with the project's key messages (Section 4). This plan covers activities foreseen primarily within WP6, leveraging inputs and participation from all consortium partners.

5.1 Project Identity & Branding

A strong and consistent visual identity is crucial for project recognition and branding. Key activities include:

Logo Development: Creation of a unique project logo. An adapted version including a QR code linking to the project website will also be utilized.

Templates: Development and use of common templates for presentations, reports, leaflets, and roll-up banners to ensure a cohesive look and feel across all materials.

Brand Guidelines: Establishment of guidelines for logo usage, colour palettes, and typography to maintain brand consistency.

Press Kit: Development of a core press kit containing project descriptions, key messages, partner information, FAQs, high-resolution logos, and potentially copyright-free images for media use.

5.2 Digital Presence

The project's online presence will serve as the primary hub for information and engagement.

Project Website:

- *Development & Launch:* The official project website (<https://www.estelar-project.eu>) will be developed and launched by M4, serving as the central information point.
- *Content:* It will host public information (project overview, partners, objectives, news, public results, contact) and potentially a private area for consortium members. Key public deliverables will be made available for download.
- *Maintenance:* A plan for regular content updates (news, blog posts, event information, results) throughout the project and for maintaining the website for at least two years post-project completion will be implemented.

- *Integration:* Partners will be encouraged to link to the ESTELAR website from their own institutional websites.
- *Analytics:* Website traffic and user engagement will be monitored using analytics tools. (Target: >1,000 hits/year).

Effective Substation Technologies for Advanced virtualization

What is ESTELAR?

ESTELAR is built on three key pillars: advanced communication strategies, a robust computational framework, and the transformative Digital Substation of the Future architecture. It enhances substation communication systems to ensure seamless, real-time integration between physical and virtual components. The project also strengthens computational capabilities through cloud and edge computing, allowing substations to process and manage vast amounts of data efficiently. Additionally, ESTELAR develops a modular, scalable substation architecture that integrates digital twinning for advanced monitoring, protection, and control.

Social Media:

- *Platforms:* Official project accounts will be established and maintained on LinkedIn (for professional/industry outreach) and potentially Bluesky (or another relevant platform for broader/research community engagement). (Target: 500+ followers on LinkedIn, 100+ on Bluesky/alternative).
- *Strategy:* A content calendar will guide regular posts, including project updates, news, event promotion, sharing of relevant content, partner highlights, and engagement with stakeholders and related initiatives. Focus will be on driving traffic to the project website and fostering discussion.

5.3 Publications

Disseminating results through appropriate publications is key to reaching scientific and technical audiences.

Scientific Publications: The consortium aims to publish at least 7 peer-reviewed scientific papers in relevant high-impact journals and conference proceedings, adhering strictly to Horizon Europe's Open Access mandates. (Target downloads: ≥ 70).

Technical / Industry Publications: Articles targeting practitioners will be pursued in relevant trade magazines and online technical portals.

Public Deliverables: All public project deliverables (e.g., D6.2, D6.3, D6.5, D6.7, D6.8, D6.10, D6.11, D6.12) will be made accessible, primarily through the project website.

5.4 Events

Active participation in and organization of events are crucial for networking, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement.

Conference & Fair Participation: The consortium will target participation (presentations, posters, booths where appropriate) in, at least, 10 key international and European conferences and fairs relevant to smart grids, substation technology, communications, cybersecurity, and energy. Initial targets include IEEE Smart Grid Comms, Enlit Europe, The Smarter-E, and IEEE ISGT.

Project Workshops:

- *Stakeholder Workshops:* At least 2 dedicated workshops will be organized (starting M12 onwards) to engage specific stakeholder groups, present progress, gather feedback, and discuss exploitation potential.
- *Local Workshops:* At least 2 local workshops (1 per pilot context) will be organized (starting M7 onwards) targeting local/regional stakeholders.

Final Project Event: A final conference will be organized towards the end of the project (M36) to showcase overall achievements, results, and future outlook. (Target participants: >100).

To facilitate the events organization, a shared calendar of events has been created to provide an overview of international events, allowing partners to easily identify suitable opportunities to disseminate the project.

Calendar						
DATE	DURATION	EVENT NAME	LOCATION	TYPE	LINK WEB	Proposed by
13/01/2025	13-17/01	Bautec expo	Munich, Germ	Expo	https://ilikever	R2M Spain
06/05/2025	6-7/05	The smarter E Europe –	Munich, Germ	Conference	https://www.th	R2M Spain
07/05/2025	7-9/05	The smarter E Europe –	Munich, Germ	Exhibition	https://www.th	R2M Spain
29/09/2025	29/09-2/10	IEEE International Confere	Toronto, Cana	Conference	https://sgc202	R2M Spain
20/10/2025		IEEE International Conference on Innovativ	Valletta, Malta	Conference	https://ieee-is	R2M Spain
18/11/2025	18-20/11	ENLIT	Bilbao, Spain	Exhibition	https://www.ej	R2M Spain
18/11/2025	18-20/11	MATELEC	Madrid, Spain	Exhibition	https://www.if	CIRCE
27/10/2025		Power Systems Develop	Amsterdam	Exhibition	https://power-	CIRCE
08/10/2025	08/10/2025	Smart Energy Congress	Madrid, Spain	Exhibition	https://enertic	CIRCE
28/10/2025	30/10/2025	GRIDexpo 2025	Düsseldorf	Exhibition	https://grid-ex	CIRCE

5.5 Communication Materials

A suite of materials will be developed to support CDE activities.

Brochure/Leaflet: A project brochure/leaflet will be created (digital and print) for distribution at events and online. (Target distribution: ≥2,500).

Poster/Roll-up: A standardized project poster and roll-up banner will be developed for use at conferences and events.

Presentations: A master presentation template will be available, with specific presentations developed for different events and audiences.

Videos: At least 2 project videos (e.g., overview, demonstrator showcase) will be produced. (Target views: ≥ 500).

Newsletters: Regular e-newsletters (e.g., bi-annually or annually) will be produced and distributed to a growing mailing list. (Target subscribers: ≥ 100).

5.6 Public Relations / Media Outreach

Efforts will be made to gain visibility through relevant media channels.

Press Releases: At least 18 press releases will be developed and distributed strategically throughout the project lifecycle, timed with key milestones, results, or events.

Media Relations: Building contacts with journalists and editors from relevant technical and energy sector media outlets.

5.7 EC Platforms & Tools

ESTELAR will leverage official European Commission channels:

- **CORDIS:** Ensuring the project information is accurate and up-to-date.
- **Horizon Results Platform:** Uploading key exploitable results to maximize their visibility.
- **Horizon Magazine / Research*eu Magazines:** Proposing project stories and results for potential features.
- **EC Social Media:** Engaging with relevant EC accounts and campaigns.

5.8 Internal Communication

Effective internal communication is foundational for successful external CDE.

Mechanisms include:

- Regular updates during consortium meetings (Steering Committee, General Assembly).
- Dedicated WP6 communication channels and meetings.

- Use of a shared internal repository (e.g., SharePoint, Teams) for CDE materials, plans, and tracking documents.

6 Exploitation Strategy (Initial)

This section outlines the initial strategy for the exploitation of results generated within the ESTELAR project. Exploitation, in this context, refers to the utilization of project outcomes – whether technical innovations, knowledge, methodologies, or software – to create tangible value beyond the project's research activities. This value can manifest as commercial products or services, contributions to standards, improvements in industrial processes, input to policy-making, or further research advancements.

This initial strategy sets the framework for identifying, assessing, protecting, and ultimately leveraging ESTELAR's results to maximize their impact. It is intrinsically linked with the communication and dissemination activities detailed earlier, as effective sharing of information is often a prerequisite for successful exploitation. This strategy will be progressively detailed and refined throughout the project lifecycle, culminating in specific exploitation plans for key results and documented in deliverables D7.3 and D7.4 (IPR Protection Plan and Exploitation Plan updates).

6.1 Approach to Exploitation

ESTELAR adopts a proactive and integrated approach to exploitation, managed within WP6 (led by R2M ES) with active participation from all partners, particularly those generating specific results. The core principles of this approach are:

Early Identification: Potential exploitable results will be identified continuously throughout the project, starting from the initial design phases and progressing through development and validation in the VTLs.

Structured Assessment: A defined methodology (inspired by established frameworks like IPER and tailored to ESTELAR's context, linked to Task 6.4) will be used to evaluate the potential (technical, market, societal) of identified results. This includes assessing innovation level, market need, potential barriers, and required IPR protection.

Prioritization: Efforts will be focused on results with the highest potential for impact and feasibility for exploitation – the Key Exploitable Results (KERs).

IPR Management Integration: Intellectual Property protection strategies will be developed in parallel with exploitation planning to ensure results are adequately safeguarded before dissemination or commercialization efforts begin (see Section 6.3 and Task 6.4).

Collaborative Planning: Exploitation pathways will be defined collaboratively involving result owners, potential users within the consortium (e.g., CUERVA,

STEDIN, SIEMENS), and exploitation experts (R2M ES), considering market analysis and business modelling inputs (Tasks 6.4, 6.5).

Alignment with C&D: Exploitation plans will leverage the communication and dissemination channels established in Section 5 to reach potential adopters, licensees, or partners.

6.2 Identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) – Preliminary List

This first version of the CDE plan includes a *preliminary* list of potential Key Exploitable Results (KERs) derived from the project's core objectives and the deliverables outlined in the Description of Action (GA Annex 1). This list is intended as a starting point and will be refined, expanded, and detailed as the project progresses and technical results mature. The assessment process (within Task 6.4 starting M12) will prioritize these and potentially others that emerge.

Preliminary List of Potential KERs:

1. **Validated DSoF Architecture:** The overall design, principles, and specifications for the Digital Substation of the Future developed and validated in WP4/WP5 (related to D4.1).
2. **Advanced Communication & Routing Strategies:** Novel or optimized protocols, tunnelling techniques, and network configurations for secure and reliable communication in virtualized substations (related to WP2, D2.1, D2.2).
3. **Computational Framework & Benchmarks:** The validated edge/cloud computing framework specifications, performance benchmarks, and orchestration strategies (related to WP3, D3.1, D3.2).
4. **Cybersecurity Solutions for Virtualized Substations:** Specific methodologies, architectural elements, or configurations enhancing the cybersecurity of DSoF (related to WP4, D4.3).
5. **vPAC Solutions & IED/PAC Digital Twins:** The virtualized PAC functions and the methodologies/tools for creating and utilizing digital twins for testing and validation (related to WP4, D4.2).
6. **Grid Data Repository & Common Data Space Approach:** Methodology and potentially tools for establishing a repository for substation data aligned with Common Data Spaces principles (related to WP2, D2.3).
7. **Power Quality (PQ) Enhancement Algorithms:** Software algorithms designed for improved PQ monitoring or mitigation suitable for deployment in the computational framework (related to WP3, D3.3).

8. **Monitoring & Evaluation Methodology/Strategy:** The framework developed in WP5 for assessing the performance and impact of virtualized substation technologies (related to D5.1).
9. **Know-how & Methodologies from VTL Testing:** Accumulated expertise and specific procedures developed for testing and validating virtualized substation components and systems in the unique VTL environments (related to WP5).

Disclaimer: This list is preliminary and illustrative. Each potential KER requires further definition, assessment, and confirmation by the relevant partners.

Detailed characterization tables will be developed and maintained internally, forming the basis for future exploitation deliverables.

6.3 IPR Management Strategy

Effective Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management is fundamental to successful exploitation. The strategy is governed by the rules set forth in the Grant Agreement (Article 16) and the Consortium Agreement (CA), which all partners have agreed upon. Key aspects include:

- **Background IP:** Background IP brought into the project by partners remains their property. It must be identified as per the CA. Access rights are granted to other partners on a royalty-free basis for carrying out their work under the project. Access for exploiting foreground results will be under Fair and Reasonable (FRAND) conditions, unless otherwise agreed in the CA.
- **Foreground IP:**
 - *Ownership:* Foreground IP generated within the project is owned by the partner(s) generating it. Rules for handling joint ownership (requiring a Joint Ownership Agreement - JOA) are detailed in the CA and GA (Annex 5).
 - *Protection:* ESTELAR aims to adequately protect valuable Foreground IP. The *type* of protection (e.g., patenting for novel hardware/algorithms, copyright for software, trade secrets/know-how for methodologies and architectures, potentially design rights) will be assessed on a case-by-case basis for each KER, considering its nature, commercial potential, and the partners' exploitation intentions. The project includes specific tasks and deliverables for developing the detailed IPR strategy and protection plans (Task 6.4, D6.4, D6.9, D6.10).
 - *Disclosure:* Partners must be mindful of disclosure rules; public dissemination (publications, presentations) may only occur *after*

decisions regarding protection have been made, following the procedures outlined in the CA.

- **IPR Registry:** An internal IPR register will be maintained (as part of D6.4/D6.9/D6.10) to track background declarations and foreground IP generation and protection status.
- **Freedom to Operate (FTO):** FTO analyses may be conducted for KERs with high commercial potential to ensure their exploitation does not infringe on existing third-party rights.

6.4 Market Analysis (Outline)

While detailed market analysis is planned for later stages (Task 6.4, M3-M12 onwards), this initial plan recognizes its necessity. The analysis will investigate, for prioritized KERs:

- Target application domains and potential markets (geographical scope, size).
 - Specific customer segments and their needs.
 - Existing competing or alternative solutions and key players.
 - Market trends, drivers, and barriers (including regulatory landscape).
- The findings will be crucial inputs for refining KER value propositions and developing viable business models and exploitation pathways.

6.5 Business Models & Commercialisation (Outline)

The development of concrete business models (Task 6.5, starting M17) and commercialization strategies is a key objective for maximizing ESTELAR's impact. This initial plan acknowledges the need to explore various pathways, potentially including:

- **Direct Use:** Partners (especially utilities and technology providers) incorporating ESTELAR results into their own operations, products, or services.
- **Licensing:** Granting licenses for protected IP (patents, software) to third parties.
- **New Products/Services:** Development of new commercial offerings based on ESTELAR results.
- **Standardization:** Contributing results and insights to relevant standardization bodies (IEC, CENELEC etc.) to influence future standards.
- **Further R&D:** Using results as a basis for subsequent research projects or collaborations.
- **Spin-offs:** Exploring the potential for creating new ventures based on specific project outcomes.

The selection of the most appropriate pathway(s) will depend on the nature of the KER, partner interests, IPR strategy, and market analysis findings. This will be further elaborated in the business model development task (T6.5) and the replication roadmaps (T6.6, D6.5, D6.11, D6.12).

7 Management, Roles, and Responsibilities

The successful implementation of the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) plan requires clear roles, responsibilities, and effective coordination among all ESTELAR consortium partners. This section outlines the management structure and the specific duties assigned to ensure the CDE objectives are met. The overall coordination of these activities resides within WP6.

7.1 Lead Partner Responsibilities

As the leader of WP6, **R2M ES** holds the primary responsibility for the overall coordination, management, and execution of the CDE strategy outlined in this plan. Key responsibilities include:

Strategic Leadership: Leading the development, implementation, monitoring, and updating of the CDE strategy and plan (D6.1, D6.6) and the Exploitation strategy and related plans (D6.4, D6.5, D6.9, D6.10, D6.11, D6.12).

Activity Coordination: Planning, scheduling, and coordinating all cross-consortium CDE activities described in Section 5.

Content Management & Production: Overseeing the creation, collection, and editing of content for various CDE channels; directly managing the project website, social media presence, newsletters, and coordinating the production of promotional materials (brochures, videos).

Monitoring and Reporting: Establishing and maintaining the C&D tracker (Annex I), collecting inputs from partners, monitoring progress against KPIs (Section 8), and preparing the WP6 contributions for periodic project reports (D6.2, D6.7, D6.8) and milestone reviews (MS2).

Facilitation & Support: Organizing and chairing WP6 meetings, facilitating stakeholder workshops (in collaboration with technical partners), providing guidance and support to partners for their CDE contributions, and managing the CDE budget within WP6.

Exploitation Coordination: Leading the process for KER identification and management (Task 6.4), coordinating the development of the IPR strategy (Task 6.4), leading business model development (Task 6.5), and coordinating the development of the replication roadmaps (Task 6.6).

7.2 Role of the Project Coordinator

As the overall Project Coordinator, **CIRCE** plays a vital role in ensuring the CDE activities align with the project's overarching goals and contractual obligations. Specific roles include:

- **Overall Oversight:** Ensuring WP6 activities are consistent with the Grant Agreement and contribute effectively to the project's expected impact.
- **Liaison with Funding Authority:** Acting as the main point of contact with CINEA/European Commission for reporting and strategic discussions, including those related to CDE impact.
- **High-Level Representation:** Representing the ESTELAR project in high-level forums and interactions where overall project vision and impact are communicated.
- **Content Contribution:** As a key technical partner and leader of WP2, providing timely and relevant technical content for dissemination and exploitation.
- **Approval Role:** Participating in the approval process for major strategic decisions related to CDE and Exploitation, as defined in the project's governance structure (Steering Committee/General Assembly).

7.3 Role of All Partners

Effective CDE is a shared responsibility requiring active participation from all beneficiaries. Each partner is expected to:

- **Contribute Content:** Provide timely, accurate, and relevant information regarding their work, technical progress, results, and participation in external activities for use in website news, blog posts, social media, newsletters, publications, and reports.
- **Participate Actively:** Engage in planned CDE activities, including attending project workshops, presenting at relevant conferences/fairs (as agreed), contributing to publications, and participating in clustering activities.
- **Leverage Networks:** Actively utilize their own institutional and professional networks to disseminate information about ESTELAR and its results to relevant audiences.
- **Provide Feedback:** Review draft CDE materials and strategic documents when requested, providing constructive feedback.
- **Manage IP:** Adhere to the IPR rules defined in the GA and CA, declare relevant Background IP, and contribute to the identification and protection strategy for Foreground IP arising from their work.
- **Track Activities:** Regularly update the central C&D Tracker (Annex I) with their relevant CDE activities (events attended, publications, significant outreach).

7.4 Role of Technical Work Package Leaders & Result Developers

Partners leading technical work packages (WP2-CIRCE, WP3-SOC-E, WP4-TUD, WP5-TUD) or developing specific KERs have a particular responsibility to:

- **Be the Primary Source:** Act as the main point of contact for R2M ES regarding the technical details, context, significance, and potential applications of the results generated within their scope of work.
- **Lead Scientific Dissemination:** Drive the preparation and submission of scientific publications and conference presentations related to their technical domain.
- **Support Exploitation Planning:** Provide essential technical and market-related input for the characterization of KERs, assessment of exploitation potential, definition of exploitation pathways, and IPR protection decisions related to their results.

7.5 Role of Associated Partner

Although not claiming costs, the Associated Partner **STEDIN** plays a valuable role by:

- **Providing Perspective:** Offering insights from a DSO perspective to ensure the relevance and applicability of ESTELAR's solutions and communication messages.
- **Network Access:** Facilitating access to relevant networks and stakeholders within their sphere of influence, where appropriate.
- **Participation:** Contributing expertise by participating in relevant project workshops, reviews, or advisory discussions.

7.6 Coordination Mechanism

Regular WP6 Meetings: Dedicated virtual or physical meetings focusing on CDE planning, progress review, and task coordination, led by R2M ES.

Consortium Meetings: Inclusion of dedicated CDE sessions in Steering Committee and General Assembly meetings for strategic alignment, reporting, and decision-making.

C&D Tracker: Use of the shared online tracker as the central tool for activity planning, monitoring, and reporting by all partners.

Shared Digital Workspace: Utilization of the project's internal collaboration platform for efficient sharing of documents, templates, calendars, and ongoing discussions related to CDE.

Direct Communication: Regular bilateral exchanges between R2M ES and individual partners as needed for specific content development or activity coordination.

7.7 Timeline (High-Level)

This section provides a high-level overview of the planned timeline for the key Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) activities within WP6, aligned with the overall project duration of 36 months. The detailed task scheduling is visually represented in the GANTT chart included in the WP6 Outline (Section 6). The timeline is broken down into key project phases:

Phase I: Foundation & Setup (Months 1-12)

Focus: Establishing the core CDE infrastructure, defining initial strategies, and launching primary communication channels.

Key Activities:

- Development and finalization of the initial CDE Strategy (leading to **D6.1 due M6**).
- Creation of Project Visual Identity (Logo, templates) (completed by M3).
- Development and launch of the Project Website and initial Social Media Presence (LinkedIn, Bluesky) (by M4).
- Start of continuous Content Creation (Blog posts, social media updates) (from M6).
- Initiation of Market Research and IPR Strategy Development (starting M3 & M6 respectively).
- Beginning of Event Planning and initial Project Clustering/Synergy activities (from M6).

Key Deliverables/Milestones:

D6.1: CDE Plan V1 (M6)

MS2: ESTELAR Initial Documentation Ready and Launch of DEC Strategy (M6)

D6.2: Dissemination & Communication Report V1 (M12)

D6.4: Knowledge Management & IPR Protection Plan V1 (M12)

D6.5: Roadmap Towards Replication V1 (M12)

Phase 2: Implementation & Engagement (Months 13-24)

Focus: Active dissemination of emerging results, intensified stakeholder engagement, refinement of exploitation plans, and mid-term strategy review.

Key Activities:

- Continuous Content Creation and Distribution (Newsletters, social media, website updates).
- Active participation in identified Conferences and Fair.
- Organization of first Stakeholder Workshops (starting M12).
- Ongoing Project Clustering activities.

- Conclusion of initial Market Research and IPR Strategy Development (ending M12).
- Initiation of KER Management and exploitation pathway development (starting M12).
- Start of Value Proposition Design for KERs (starting M17).
- Start of Business Model Canvas Development (starting M20).
- Strategy refinement and KPI tracking.

Key Deliverables:

D6.6: DEC Plan Update (M24)

D6.7: Dissemination & Communication Report V2 (M24)

D6.9: Knowledge Management & IPR Protection Plan V2 (M24)

D6.11: Roadmap Towards Replication V2 (M24)

Phase 3: Consolidation, Exploitation & Finalization (Months 25–36)

Focus: Disseminating final validated results, finalizing exploitation plans and business models, developing the replication roadmap, and ensuring project legacy.

Key Activities:

- Intensified dissemination of VTL testing outcomes and final results (linked to **MS7 at M28**).
- Continued content creation, event participation, and stakeholder engagement.
- Finalization of Business Model Canvas Development and Financial Planning.
- Development of Replication Roadmap (Barrier Analysis, Scale-up Strategy, Implementation Planning).
- Implementation of IPR protection measures for prioritized KERs.
- Preparation and execution of the Final Project Event/Outreach
- Final reporting and consolidation of all CDE activities.

Key Deliverables/Milestones:

MS7: Main Outcomes from VTLs Testing and Validation Ready for Upscaling (M28)

D6.3: Project Synergies Report (M36)

D6.8: Dissemination & Communication Report – Final Version (M36)

D6.10: Knowledge Management & IPR Protection Plan – Final Version (M36)

D6.12: Roadmap Towards Replication – Final Version (M36)

MS8: Finalization of ESTELAR (M36)

This high-level timeline provides a roadmap for the CDE activities within ESTELAR. The specific timing and execution of tasks are subject to refinement based on project progress and emerging opportunities, coordinated continuously by the WP6 lead (R2M ES).

8 Monitoring, Evaluation, and KPIs

To ensure the effectiveness of the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) activities and to track progress towards the objectives outlined in Section 2, a robust monitoring and evaluation framework will be implemented throughout the ESTELAR project lifecycle. This framework relies on the continuous collection of data, the tracking of specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and periodic evaluation to allow for adaptive management of the CDE strategy.

8.1 Monitoring Approach

The monitoring of CDE activities will be a continuous process managed by the WP6 leader (R2M ES) with active contributions from all consortium partners. The primary tools and methods for monitoring include:

C&D Tracker: A shared spreadsheet (template provided in Annex I) will be used as the central repository for partners to log their CDE activities in near real-time. This includes participation in events, publications submitted/accepted, specific communication actions undertaken (e.g., significant social media campaigns, press releases issued via institutional channels), and key contacts made within the dissemination network. Partners are responsible for keeping their contributions up-to-date.

Digital Analytics:

- *Website:* Standard web analytics tools (e.g., Google Analytics or similar privacy-compliant alternatives) will be used to track key metrics such as total visits, unique visitors, page views, traffic sources, geographic location of visitors, and user engagement time.
- *Social Media:* Native analytics dashboards provided by the chosen platforms (LinkedIn, Bluesky) will be used to monitor follower growth, post reach, impressions, engagement rates (likes, shares, comments), and audience demographics.

Event Reporting: Following participation in or organization of significant events (conferences, workshops, fairs), partners will submit a concise event report (template provided in Annex II) to the WP6 leader, summarizing the activity, audience reached, key outcomes, and contacts made.

Publication Tracking: Partners will report submitted and accepted/published scientific and technical articles, including details for Open Access verification and repository linking (e.g., DOIs). Download/citation metrics will be tracked where available.

Qualitative Feedback: Feedback regarding CDE activities will be actively sought during stakeholder workshops, consortium meetings, and direct interactions.

Monitoring data will be compiled and reviewed regularly by the WP6 leader and presented during project meetings (SC/GA) and within the periodic project reports submitted to the granting authority.

8.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) - Initial Targets

Specific, measurable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been defined to quantify the reach, engagement, and impact of ESTELAR's CDE activities. The targets listed below represent the cumulative goals for the **entire 36-month project duration**, based on the content in Section 5. Progress towards these targets will be monitored continuously and reported periodically. These targets are ambitious yet realistic but may be subject to review and adjustment during the project based on evaluation outcomes.

Communication KPIs:

- **Project Website:** > 1,000 hits/year (*Note: This implies a target of >3,000 hits over the project duration*)
- **Social Media:** > 500 followers on LinkedIn; > 100 followers on Bluesky (or chosen alternative)
- **Press Releases Issued:** ≥ 18
- **Video Views (Total):** ≥ 500
- **Promotional Materials (Brochures/Leaflets Distributed):** ≥ 2,500

Dissemination KPIs:

- **Scientific/Technical Publications:** ≥ 7 papers (peer-reviewed, Open Access compliant)
- **Technical Publication Downloads/Accesses:** ≥ 70 (where trackable)
- **Conference/Fair Attendances:** ≥ 10 distinct events where ESTELAR is presented
- **Organized Workshops (Project-level/Stakeholder):** ≥ 2
- **Local Workshops (Pilot-context focused):** ≥ 2 (at least 1 per VTL context)
- **Final Project Event Participants:** > 100 (*Note: Target adapted from WP6 outline, assuming >100 is more specific than >60 in GA MSI for overall outreach*)
- **E-Newsletter Subscribers:** ≥ 100

Networking KPIs:

- **Collaboration with related EU Projects:** ≥ 6 active collaborations (e.g., joint activities, knowledge exchange)
- **Joint Webinars/Activities:** ≥ 4 held with cluster projects or key initiatives

- **Engagement with Relevant Networks/Associations:** ≥ 6 active engagements/collaboration agreements established

Exploitation KPIs:

- **Business Models Developed:** ≥ 3 (for prioritized KERs)
- **Patent Applications Filed:** ≥ 2 (or other forms of IP protection initiated as appropriate)
- **Commercial Exploitation Agreements (or equivalent MoU/NDA):** ≥ 2 initiated/signed
- **Letters of Interest/Intent from Potential Adopters/Customers:** > 10 received

8.3 Evaluation Process

The monitoring data and progress against KPIs will be systematically evaluated to assess the effectiveness of the CDE strategy and activities. This evaluation process will include:

Periodic Reviews: CDE progress and performance against KPIs will be formally reviewed as part of the project's periodic reporting cycles (typically M12, M24, M36) and discussed within consortium meetings (SC/GA).

Performance Analysis: The collected data will be analysed to understand which channels, messages, and activities are most effective in reaching different target audiences and achieving specific objectives. This includes analysing website traffic patterns, social media engagement, event feedback, publication impact (where measurable), and progress on exploitation indicators.

Qualitative Assessment: Beyond quantitative metrics, qualitative feedback from stakeholders, partners, and event participants will be considered to gauge the clarity of messages, the relevance of activities, and the overall perception of the project.

Strategy Adaptation: Based on the evaluation findings, the WP6 leader, in consultation with the Project Coordinator and relevant partners, will propose adjustments to the CDE strategy, activities plan, channel mix, messaging, or even KPI targets if necessary. This ensures the CDE plan remains a dynamic tool aligned with the project's evolving needs and opportunities.

This continuous cycle of monitoring, evaluation, and adaptation is crucial for maximizing the effectiveness and impact of ESTELAR's Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation efforts.

9 Risk Assessment for CDE Activities

While a comprehensive CDE plan is in place, potential risks could hinder the effective execution of communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, potentially impacting the project's overall visibility and impact. This section identifies key risks related to WP6 and outlines corresponding mitigation strategies to proactively manage them. This assessment draws upon the project's overall risk analysis (GA pp. 103-105) where relevant, and adds CDE-specific considerations.

9.1 Identification of Risks

The following potential risks associated with ESTELAR's CDE activities have been identified:

Table 2. WP6 Risk Identification (Likelihood/Impact assessment is preliminary and should be reviewed by the consortium: Low/Medium/High)

Risk ID	Risk Description	Likelihood (L)	Impact (I)	Related GA Risk(s)
CDE-R1	Low visibility and stakeholder engagement: Target audiences are not reached effectively, or stakeholders show limited interest/participation in project activities (workshops, feedback requests).	Medium	High	GA Risk 14
CDE-R2	Delays in project results: Significant delays in achieving key technical milestones or producing results impact the timeliness and relevance of planned dissemination and communication actions.	Medium	Medium	-
CDE-R3	Ineffective communication/dissemination channels or messages: Chosen channels fail to reach target audiences, or messages are unclear, too technical, or not perceived as relevant.	Medium	Medium	GA Risk 13
CDE-R4	IPR / Confidentiality constraints: Issues related to intellectual property ownership, protection strategies, or confidentiality agreements hinder timely or open dissemination of certain results, or create conflicts during exploitation planning.	Low	High	GA Risk 6
CDE-R5	Insufficient partner contribution: Partners provide limited content, participate minimally in events, or do not actively use their networks for dissemination, reducing overall CDE effectiveness.	Low	Medium	-
CDE-R6	Ineffective exploitation strategy / Lack of market uptake: Identified KERs fail to attract interest, business models prove unviable, or exploitation pathways are blocked by market/regulatory barriers.	Medium	High	GA Risk 12

CDE-R7	Subpar replication/scalability communication: Failure to effectively communicate the replication potential and scalability of ESTELAR solutions hinders uptake beyond initial partners/VTLs.	Medium	High	GA Risk 11
CDE-R8	Weak internal communication: Poor communication <i>within</i> the consortium regarding CDE plans, responsibilities, or result progress hampers coordinated external CDE efforts.	Low	Medium	GA Risk 2, GA Risk 13

9.2 Mitigation Strategies

For each identified risk, the following mitigation strategies will be implemented:

CDE-R1 (Low visibility/engagement): Implement a multi-channel approach tailored to specific audiences. Proactively map and engage stakeholders from the outset, clearly communicating the project's value proposition. Use partner networks extensively for outreach. Regularly monitor engagement metrics (KPIs) and adapt the strategy (channels, content focus) based on performance. Organize targeted workshops focusing on stakeholder needs. (Ref GA Risk 14 Mitigation)

CDE-R2 (Delays in results): Maintain a flexible CDE plan and content calendar. If technical results are delayed, focus communication on project progress, challenges overcome, methodology, intermediate findings, and partner expertise. Disseminate validated results promptly once available. Ensure close coordination between technical WPs and WP6.

CDE-R3 (Ineffective channels/messages): Conduct thorough audience analysis to inform channel selection and message tailoring. Pre-test key messages where possible. Utilize diverse formats (text, visual, video). Monitor channel performance via analytics and KPIs, adjusting the mix as needed. Solicit feedback on communication clarity during events/interactions.

CDE-R4 (IPR/Confidentiality constraints): Establish clear IPR management procedures early via the Consortium Agreement and dedicated IPR plan (D6.4 etc.). Foster open discussion among partners regarding background/foreground IP and exploitation intentions. Implement a clear process for approving public disclosures (publications, presentations) to ensure IP is protected beforehand. Seek legal advice if complex IPR issues arise. (Ref GA Risk 6 Mitigation)

CDE-R5 (Insufficient partner contribution): Clearly define partner roles and responsibilities for CDE in this plan and the CA. Implement the C&D tracker and provide regular reminders/support from WP6 lead. Highlight partner contributions in project communications (website, newsletters). Integrate CDE reporting into regular project meeting agendas.

CDE-R6 (Ineffective exploitation/uptake): Implement a structured KER identification and validation process involving technical and market expertise. Conduct thorough market analysis (T6.4). Develop realistic business models (T6.5) with stakeholder input. Actively engage potential adopters throughout the project. Develop clear replication roadmaps (T6.6).

CDE-R7 (Subpar replication communication): Specifically address scalability and replicability in dissemination materials, workshops, and exploitation plans (T6.6). Highlight results from diverse VTL environments. Use case studies and lessons learned (D6.3) to demonstrate adaptability.

CDE-R8 (Weak internal communication): Utilize established internal communication channels effectively (meetings, shared platform). Ensure clear communication flows between WP leaders and WP6. Maintain an updated internal repository for CDE plans and materials. Implement the democratic and dialectic communication approach mentioned in GA Risk 6/13 Mitigation.

The WP6 leader (R2M ES), in coordination with the Project Coordinator (CIRCE) and the Steering Committee, will be responsible for overseeing the implementation of these mitigation strategies and monitoring the identified risks throughout the project duration. The risk register will be reviewed and updated as part of the periodic project reporting cycle.

10 Conclusions

This deliverable, D6.1, establishes the foundational **Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) Plan** for the ESTELAR project. It provides the initial strategy, objectives, target audiences, key messages, channels, tools, and activities designed to maximize the project's visibility, impact, and the future uptake of its results throughout its 36-month duration and beyond.

The plan outlines a comprehensive and integrated approach, recognizing that effective communication, targeted dissemination, and proactive exploitation planning are interconnected and essential for achieving ESTELAR's ambitious goals in advancing substation virtualization. Key elements defined include:

- **Clear Objectives:** Focused on raising awareness, disseminating results, engaging stakeholders, supporting exploitation, and ensuring compliance.
- **Defined Audiences:** Identification of crucial stakeholder groups, from system operators and technology providers to researchers and policymakers.
- **Strategic Messaging:** Tailored key messages designed to resonate with different audiences and highlight ESTELAR's value proposition.
- **Multi-channel Approach:** A diverse set of channels and tools, including a project website, social media, publications, events, and direct engagement, will be employed.
- **Initial Exploitation Framework:** An early strategy for identifying Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and managing Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) has been established, laying the groundwork for detailed exploitation planning in later stages.
- **Management Structure:** Clear roles and responsibilities have been assigned, with WP6 (led by R2M ES) coordinating the effort with active involvement from all partners.
- **Monitoring & Evaluation:** A framework based on specific KPIs and regular reviews is in place to track progress and ensure adaptive management of the CDE strategy.
- **Risk Management:** Potential risks related to CDE activities have been identified, along with corresponding mitigation strategies.

This document serves as the primary reference for all consortium partners involved in CDE activities. It is a **living document**; the strategies, activities, and KPIs presented herein will be continuously monitored, evaluated, and refined in subsequent plan updates (D6.6) and reports (D6.2, D6.7, D6.8) based on project progress, emerging results, and stakeholder feedback.

The ESTELAR consortium is committed to implementing this plan diligently, ensuring that the project's significant contributions to grid modernization, resilience, security, and the clean energy transition are effectively communicated and its innovative results achieve maximum impact across Europe.

11 References

No references are included in this Deliverable.

12 Annexes

12.1 Annex I: Communication & Dissemination (C&D) Tracker Template

Firs version of the templates are included in this deliverable.

They will be adjusted based on the F&T Portal fields and new identified needs during project implementation.

Templates included: Event Log, Publication Log, Communication Activities Log, Dissemination Conference Log

12.2 Annex III: Initial List of Target Dissemination Outlets (Journals, Conferences)

List of target dissemination outlets both for journals and conferences.

DATE	DURATION	EVENT NAME	LOCATION	TYPE	LINK WEB	Proposed b
13/01/2025	13-17/01	Bautec expo	Munich, Germany	Expo	https://ilikevents.com/event/	R2M Spain
06/05/2025	6-7/05	The smarter E Europe – Europe's Largest AI	Munich, Germany	Conference	https://www.thesmartere.de/	R2M Spain
07/05/2025	7-9/05	The smarter E Europe – Europe's Largest AI	Munich, Germany	Exhibition	https://www.thesmartere.de/	R2M Spain
29/09/2025	29/09-2/10	IEEE International Conference on Communi	Toronto, Canada	Conference	https://sgc2025.ieee-smartg	R2M Spain
20/10/2025		IEEE International Conference on Innovative	Valletta, Malta	Conference	https://ieee-isqt-europe.org/	R2M Spain
18/11/2025	18-20/11	ENLIT	Bilbao, Spain	Exhibition	https://www.enlit-europe.com	R2M Spain
18/11/2025	18-20/11	MATELEC	Madrid, Spain	Exhibition	https://www.ifema.es/matele	CIRCE
27/10/2025		Power Systems Development Congress	Amsterdam	Exhibition	https://power-europe.com/	CIRCE
08/10/2025	08/10/2025	Smart Energy Congress	Madrid, Spain	Exhibition	https://enertic.org/congreso/	CIRCE
28/10/2025	30/10/2025	GRIDexpo 2025	Düsseldorf	Exhibition	https://grid-expo.com/en/	CIRCE

1. IEEE Access

- **Open Access:** Fully open (mandatory)
- **Focus:** Smart grids, automation, digital substations, electrical systems
- **Advantages:** Rapid review process, highly visible, widely used by EU projects

2. Energy Reports (*Elsevier*)

- **Open Access:** Fully open (Gold OA)
- **Focus:** Energy systems, smart grids, planning, digital energy infrastructures
- **Advantages:** Lower cost, indexed in Scopus and Web of Science

3. IET Smart Grid (*Wiley / IET*)

- **Open Access:** Fully open (mandatory)
- **Focus:** Grid architecture, communication systems, smart substations, grid automation
- **Advantages:** High technical relevance, peer-reviewed, IEEE-aligned

4. Journal of Modern Power Systems and Clean Energy (*Springer / IEEE*)

- **Open Access:** Optional
- **Focus:** Modern power systems, renewable energy integration, clean energy technologies
- **Advantages:** High credibility, supported by the China Electric Power Research Institute

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